

CONSTRUCTION OF 2.5kVA SOLAR BASED

INVERTER SYSTEM

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CERTIFICATION

This project report construction of 2.5kVA solar based inverter system was carried out by the following students:

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty God, the Most Gracious and the Most Merciful for seeing us through the process of this project. It is also dedicated to our parents for their prayers and financial support during the period of the project.

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ABSTRACT

This project addresses the construction of a solar-powered inverter system for the efficient conversion of energy in residential applications. The designed system makes use of solar panels, which act as renewable sources of direct current for storing in the battery and converting to alternating current through an inverter for household appliances. Main components of an inverter system include the oscillation unit, amplification unit, and transformation unit, with each playing an important role in DC-to-stable-AC conversion. Pure sine wave inverters are used efficiently in high utilization to allow minimal harmonic distortion for sensitive electronic devices. The calculations of battery capacity, inverter power rating, and the number of MOSFETs required in each arm are presented for optimized backup time and power delivery. The design also integrates power factor consideration and MPPT for efficient utilization of solar energy. Testing and evaluation show that the system performs reliably and efficiently in converting solar energy to household AC loads, hence proving the workability of renewable energy systems in dependence reduction on grid electricity. The contribution of this project to sustainable energy applies the use of cost-effective and eco-friendly alternatives for day-to-day needs in power consumption.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background Information

Solar-based inverter systems aid in the conversion of DC electricity generated by solar panels into AC, which is necessary for household, business, and industrial applications. Because solar panels generate DC from sunlight, most electrical systems require AC; hence, inverters are quite significant in integrating solar power into the grid. Other than pure DC-to-AC conversion, the work of an inverter is to regulate the flow of electricity to meet the required voltage and frequency needed for safe use. Inverters can basically let solar energy apply practically by becoming one of the most exciting sustainable power sources.

Solar inverters play a key role in a photovoltaic system, which enables DC conversions into AC, a standard for most electrical devices. (Arslan, 2022) wrote that inverters enable solar power systems to connect with the grid by making sure the electricity produced falls within the range of the utility frequency requirements; thus, making the energy usable within households and commercial settings. In off-grid systems, solar inverters provide appliances directly with AC power. To this end, it guarantees energy supply even without access to the grid. Thus, basically, an inverter is crucial in making solar energy viable to be utilized instead of conventional sources of power.

Technological development significantly increased the efficiency of solar converters. For instance, multi-level converters provide better classes of AC waveforms at the output and a decrease in total harmonic distortion (THD) with increased smoothness in energy flow and higher stability in the entire system (Arslam, 2022). Hybrid converters work with battery storage in tandem with the solar one and enhance energy management

to store excess power for later use. The systems are integrated with MPPT technology for the regulation and optimization of solar panel performance when environmental conditions change (Nasir et al., 2023). It is only such inventions that assure better reliability and efficiency in solar power systems.

The use of solar inverters implies imposing considerable economic and environmental advantages in long-term applications. It improves the efficiency of solar systems to cut down the energy cost of a developed system by reducing the overreliance on grid electricity while assuring energy independence. The solar inverters are also eco-friendly, given that they enable the utilization of clean and renewable energies, thus the carbon emissions are tremendously reduced. In this respect, facilities of larger scales, like airports and industrial plants, will enjoy smaller carbon footprints, considering that solar energy will lessen reliance on fossil fuels (Ramya et al., 2024).

1.2 Problem Statement

Unreliable grid electricity supply causes daily disruptions and dampens economic activities in many developing regions around the world. Furthermore, the frequent power outages in those regions, along with higher reliance on fossil fuels, tend to lower energy sustainability with environmental health. While solar energy could effectively sort out the issue, efficient and cost-effective conversion of solar energy to usable electricity has remained a serious challenge.

The root of the problem is the inability to have cost-effective and efficient solar-powered inverters that can reliably convert DC energy from solar panels into AC energy used in household appliances. On one hand, inverter designs do suffer from high costs, inefficiency in power conversion, and difficulties operating under a variety of loads, especially in off-grid areas where quality and stability of power are very important.

The above challenges form the basis of this research work, which aims to construct a solar-based 2.5kVA inverter. This will ensure that households and small business enterprises have an assured dependable supply of energy at reasonably affordable costs. The inverter will ensure efficient energy conversion, handle variable loads, and provide a sustainable alternative to conventional fossil-fuel-powered systems.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This work is significantly important both from the practical and environmental point of view. From the practical viewpoint, it is envisaged that this work will provide a lasting solution to the general problem of power shortages but most especially in the rural areas and where there is no reasonable electricity supply. The 2.5kVA solar inverter will be highly affordable and efficient; hence, it can be employed by a wide range of people, from households down to small-scale businesses. Being affordable and easy to use, it will reduce dependence on costly and environmentally harming alternatives like diesel generators, hence forming a more sustainable power solution.

On an environmental level, the technology of solar-based inverters is contributory in further reducing carbon emissions by limiting the use of fossil fuels. Solar energy, much like other forms of renewable resources, is a clean energy source. Harnessing it effectively through the use of inverter systems will, therefore, go a long way in responding to climate change through global attempts at encouraging greener alternatives to energy. A successful implementation would thus serve as a model for further innovations in renewable energy technologies, encouraging more research and development into this field. This work would, therefore, help in the wide adaptation of renewable systems of energy by demonstrating feasibility and benefits in the use of solar inverters.

1.4 Motivation

This research is motivated by the increasing need for sustainable energy supplies in regions suffering from an unreliable electricity supply. As the world gradually moves toward renewable energy, much emphasis needs to be put on the development of efficient systems that tap solar power. This personal interest in developing green energy technologies is very important and contributes to undertaking the research to solve the energy crisis.

1.5 Aims and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the work is the construction of a high-efficiency 2.5kVA solar-based inverter capable of converting DC from the solar panel into AC with maximum efficiency.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Construct a highly efficient 2.5kVA inverter using solar panels capable of converting DC from the solar panel to AC.
- ii. Implement the actual prototype of the solar-based inverter using locally sourced components.
- iii. Test the performance of the inverter under different load conditions and establish its reliability.
- iv. Carry out the cost-effectiveness analysis of the solar-based inverter against conventional power solutions. Contribute to the development of workable sustainable energy solutions in regions with unstable power supplies.

1.6 Scope of the Project

The project entails construction and installation of a 2.5kVA solar-based inverter system that incorporates the integration of solar panels, batteries, and pure sine wave inverter.

1.7 Thesis Outline

The project is organized as follows:

i. Chapter 1: Introduction

Introduction to the research problem: motivation, significance, and objectives; a general outline of the thesis is given.

ii. Chapter 2: Literature Review

In this chapter, prior research on the subject of solar inverters will be discussed by reviewing the key developments, technologies, and gaps in existing literature related to the study.

iii. Chapter 3: Design Methodology

This chapter deals with explaining how the inverter system was implemented. The construction approach that will be adopted, the selection of components, and the integration of the already available inverter are discussed.

iv. Chapter 4: Testing, Results and Discussion

Chapter four presents the results for the tests conducted on the inverter system. It consists of discussions and analysis related to performance, efficiency, and stability tests that were conducted under various conditions.

v. Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendation

In this chapter, the conclusion and recommendations for further studies are summarized. Reflections are made on the insight gained, and contemplation on areas that need to be investigated or further improved are considered.

CHAPTER TWO
LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Historical Background

From the time the scientific world discovered the photoelectric effect back in the 19th century solar power technology has been on an evolutionary path. Discovered by a French physics enthusiast named Edmond Becquerel in 1839, this phenomenon laid the groundwork for a way to convert sunlight into electrical energy. Actually, Becquerel laid the first stone in exploring solar energy, and from there, solar energy turned into the crucial part of renewable energy sources (Nag et al., 2022).

With the years passing and the demand for renewable sources of energy growing, efforts toward improvement in the field of efficiency and cost of photovoltaic cells started to come to the fore. Over the decades, much effort has been put into making solar energy develop from a niche technology into a mainstream source of energy. Over the last few years, the development of PV technologies has been marked by, in general, three distinct generations of solar cells (Jasim , 2023). First-generation solar cells, based on silicon, formed the foundation for the solar cell technology in the very beginning. The second generation saw the development and introduction of thin-film technologies, adding flexibility but reducing production costs. Today, third-generation PV technologies include organic and perovskite cells, promising even further efficiency and cost reductions, hence expanding the boundaries of what solar power can do (Hasan et al., 2023).

A critical innovation in modern solar power technologies has been the integration of energy storage solutions into solar power. Energy storage solutions address one of the major challenges to solar power: its intermittency. These systems ensure the energy supply is steady and reliable even when the sun does not come out because it stores excess energy produced during peak sunlight hours. Such development has played a

key role in the improvement of grid interface and, therefore, making the solar energy feasible and reliable (Hasan et al., 2023).

Apart from pure technological novelties, the existing applications of solar power technology testify to its growing adaptability and relevance. A striking illustration of this trend is the recent constructions of floating solar power plants, including the widely known Cirata Reservoir project. An installation like this would maximize energy output by utilizing a water surface and address the issue of land scarcity, thus also creating more options for developing solar power for heavily populated areas. This shows that solar technology can be adapted to a wide variety of environments, enhancing the utility and efficiency of the technology (Febrian et al., 2023).

Early generations of inverters used Darlington transistors prominently due to their capabilities for delivering current proportional to the load. However, such transistors inherently possessed inefficiency constraints: higher switching losses and thermal management problems. The introduction of FETs-also known as Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor FETs, or MOSFETs-was a serious breakthrough. FETs reduce switching losses greatly and improve the inverter efficiency because they have higher input impedance and lower on-resistance compared with Darlington pairs. This shift enabled the conversion of power more efficiently, hence reducing generated heat, which was one of the factors contributing to modern inverters' better performance (Siemieniec et al., 2022).

In the era of integrated circuits, a new development in the technology of inverters occurred in the 1990s. It was these integrated circuits that allowed sophisticated energy management systems that significantly optimized the performance of inverters. Integrated circuits, besides the miniaturization and integration of complex control

functions, allowed more precise and reliable inverter operations. In 1993, a milestone reached was the first processors for controlling inverter and charger systems. This processor would hence be able to give advanced algorithms for control and real-time processing, therefore enhancing efficiency and functionality for inverters (Guo, 2023); (Lin et al., 2022).

2.2 Technological Advancements in Inverter Systems

Recent development in inverter design is targeted at efficiency improvements in grid-connected photovoltaic systems. One of the most important innovations is transformerless inverter designs, as traditional transformers are not required, hence reducing weight and cost, and also the associated losses. The design choice is highly related to this effect apart from the overall efficiency of the whole system, enhancing a sleeker and cost-effective solution (Shahakar et al., 2022). Other new topologies of fresh circuits and their PWM techniques will be continuously brainstormed in optimizing the performances of the inverter with a view to refining the switching processes to better performance with minimum harmonic distortion (Guo, 2023).

Recently, with the increasing interest in inverters' applications, their development of control strategies has shifted its direction to better performance. Some of the advanced techniques, which have been remarkably field-oriented and had improved controlling of motors in electric vehicles, are Field-Oriented Control (FOC) and Space Vector Modulation (SVM). FOC operates on the precise regulation of motor torque and speed, and it ensures the optimal switching in SVM to reduce harmonic distortion and increase its efficiency. The various strategies thus represent the easy variability and adaptability of modern inverters toward meeting the diversified performance requirement for their varying applications (Da Silva et al., 2023).

Integration to the grid has been changing from simple grid-following (GFL) approaches to more advanced grid-forming techniques (GFM). Conventionally, GFL inverters have followed the grid voltage and frequency; this creates some problems in case the grid has low inertia. Simultaneously, GFM inverters contribute to grid stability through the active control of voltage and frequency, hence allowing for better system stability and reliability. This is critical to the development of integrating renewable energy sources into the grid by adding resiliency and improving overall grid performance (Casey et al., 2023).

2.3 Integration of Energy Storage

Energy storage systems integrated into the inverter play an important role in this respect, since the integration of renewable energy sources into power grids is receiving increased interest due to their intermittency. Different types of ESSs-batteries and capacitors-are very important for enhancing the operation of inverter-based systems.

Batteries are central to energy storage and bidirectional energy exchange. They ensure stability in inverter-based systems, especially when the share of renewable sources of energy is on the rise. The batteries neutralize the intermittent nature of renewable energy by storing excess produced power and utilizing it when there is a deficit, thereby smoothing out the output (Kamalasadan et al., 2023).

Capacitors, especially supercapacitors, are a very efficient method for high-power storage. They handle transient loads much better and increase the efficiency of a system in general (Enobakhare et al., 2022). Supercapacitors can take sudden fluctuations and peak demands when used in conjunction with batteries and remove some burdens from the batteries, thus improving overall performance(Tashakor, 2023).

Hybrid systems where batteries and supercapacitors are integrated leverage the respective strengths of such technologies. This hybrid improves system performance because it reduces the peak load from the batteries, thereby reducing the consumption and increasing the life span of the batteries and generally the reliability of the energy storage system (Enobakhare et al. 2022).

The Multi-Source Inverters are targeted for active control of different energy sources with a key focus on the reduction of power losses, enhancing efficiency. A multi-source inverter implements multiple energy sources, including hybrid storage systems, by reducing losses of power because of better switching and control strategies (Ebrahimi et al., 2022).

2.4 Role of Integrated Circuits (ICs)

The integrated circuit has transformed electronics, bringing much better performance to the inverters and improved control processors. Miniaturization and integration of more and more functions on a single chip have been the prime reasons for their significant improvements in efficiency and reliability in a variety of applications.

ICs are vast factors that enable compact designs, ensure energy efficiency, and provide high-speed operations. Such development phases make ICs necessary not only in consumer electronics but also in the field of industrial automation. Reducing complex circuitry on a single chip, these ICs reduce physical space and power consumption and further enhance the speed of operation along with ensuring better reliability (Kalmuratov et al., 2024).

The leap from Small Scale Integration (SSI) to Very Large Scale (VLSI) increased the number of transistors that can fit on a chip by leaps and bounds. Such evolution

increased the functionality and performance capability, enabling complex and efficient electronic systems to be realized (Karimullah et al., 2024).

The integration of functions of digital signal processing and control into the ICs has considerably strengthened the designs of inverters. This makes them increase the power conversion efficiency by reducing losses and hence gives them reliability and effectiveness in performance. High-speed signal integrity testing, which advanced ICs have made possible, is important for stable performance at high speeds, the key to reliability for inverters (Li, 2024).

Advanced IC technologies have enabled the building of modern control processors with superior processing capabilities. Such processors enable the realization of sophisticated control algorithms that are actually the backbone of optimizing system performance. Further optimizations in data transmission speed, as made possible by the development of EDR technology, realized real-time control and responsiveness in several applications-inverters inclusive (He, 2023).

2.5 Comparison of Different Inverter Technologies

The diversity in the technologies of solar inverters were compared, and large differences were seen in performance and efficiency. Such huge differences were found in suitability for application: each type of inverter has its specific advantages and disadvantages, related to effectiveness in different situations.

Pure sine wave inverters generate high-quality electrical power with total harmonic distortion of less than 5%. These achieve a very impressive efficiency in power at 200W load, and most importantly, this type works well on sensitive electronic devices that require clean and stable power. They also can deliver quality power with minimal

distortion to ensure the optimum performance of an application where power integrity is of prime importance (Mustikasari et al., 2023).

The Modified Sine Wave Inverters, on the other hand, are cheaper but with higher total harmonic distortion (THD), lower efficiency rated at 81.50%. These are less efficient inverters compared to pure sine wave inverters, and because of this fact, they are generally less suitable for applications that demand high-quality power. They can generally be used in situations that are not so demanding because cost considerations will outweigh the need for power precision (Mustikasari et al., 2023).

Multilevel Inverters (MLI) topologies, like the five-level NPC (neutral point clamped) inverter, have some notable advantages, such as reduced voltage stress, reduced harmonic distortion, and high efficiency. Due to the performance advantages of voltage handling and minimum harmonic effects, these topologies are highly recommended for solar applications. Their contribution to design improvement in a solar-powered system facilitates efficiency and reliability; therefore, they become the HOT choice for high-performance solar energy applications. This is also reflected in the work of (Suryawanshi et al., 2022).

They have great importance for efficiency and application purposes in solar power systems. Among the many different converters, the non-inverting buck-boost converter is seen to have an efficiency of nearly 95%. This will be greatly helpful in ensuring that energy conversion is optimized within the solar power systems, with the energy being effectively used without any loss (Mishra et al., 2022).

Moreover, the converter-based OLTCs (On-Load Tap Changers) are also desired to operate at lower transient voltage and provide improved voltage regulation in load applications, such as a diode-clamped multilevel inverter. This makes it very useful in

applications that need highly accurate levels of voltage, further improving the performance and reliability of electrical load management accordingly (Babaei et al., 2022).

2.6 Factors affecting Inverter Lifespan

Various critical variables, including environmental conditions, site characteristics of installation challenges, and degradation rates of the panels, have driven the life span of solar-based inverters. A proper understanding of all these elements in detail will help in enhancing the reliability of inverters and optimizing operational time. Similarly, monitoring and schedules for maintenance are necessary to timely identify signs of wear and to address potential problems before they spiral out of control, hence extending the life durability and efficiency of the entire system.

One factor that acts as the main dominator of variance in the lifetime of the inverter is climate. The inverters that are installed in hot climates usually suffer from accelerated degradation due to increased thermal stress. Long exposure to such a high temperature can reduce the efficiency and shorten the life of the inverter remarkably. Managing thermal loading becomes key to their performance assurance in such long-term scenarios. Moreover, the development of humidity and dust in specific areas encourages component degradation. In order to avoid such conditions, protection ways like using enclosure or air cooling systems are used to protect the inverter against such climatic conditions (Alavi et al., 2024).

The angle of tilt applied to the PV panels is another crucial influential factor on the performance of the inverter. Energy production and reliability also are functions of the tilt angle which the panels are installed. Appropriately optimized tilt angles enhance

energy generation and reduce stress on the inverter hence possibly elongating the life of the operation of the inverter variable (Bouguerra et al., 2020).

Geographical variability is another major critical influential factor on inverter lifetime. Different locations show different solar irradiance and temperature profiles, affecting the thermal stress on inverters directly. It may make the degradation of the inverter faster by reducing its efficiency in regions with high temperatures or intense solar exposure (Chanekar et al., 2020). Apart from temperature, altitude and air quality also play an important role, with higher altitudes reducing the density of the air, which again, in turn, affects the dissipation of heat. Poor air quality or pollution may contribute to dust build-up, thus demanding more frequent cleaning and maintenance.

Besides that, inverter lifetime is closely related to the degradation rates of PV panels. Panels degrade at different rates depending on the region and affect the overall efficiency of the system. For example, panel degradation in hot areas like Arizona can yield a 54% deviation in the estimates of lifespan when there are deficiencies in taking proper account of such factors, which underlines the importance of regular maintenance and monitoring in such climates (Sangwongwanich et al., 2017).

2.7 Economic Considerations

A microinverter-based solar PV system designed for a low-income household has shown quite a remarkable payback period, thus being economically viable, especially for rural electrification. The key word in the design of the system is cost-effectiveness in cases where access to the grid is negligible or non-existent. In fact, it has made the use of microinverters very popular for small, decentralized solar installations, as studies have shown that they are quite effective in lowering upfront costs, with long-term savings as part of the eventual reward of using them (Ruchira et al., 2022).

Hybrid solar-inverter systems have also become very promising, considering that there is a reduction in reliance on fossil fuels and other environmental benefits. An estimated payback period in a hybrid system, or the combination of solar energy with the traditional sources of power, of roughly five years points out that transition to renewable sources of energy is both economically viable and ecologically beneficial in urban and rural areas (Chanekar et al., 2020).

The choice of inverter size is one of the major factors influencing the financial returns on solar power plants. As much as larger inverters tend to increase energy yield due to their capability of handling high power loads, they also tend to have high initial costs. This trade-off, therefore, calls for careful consideration in view of attaining the right balance between a setup that can maximize energy output while keeping the project financially viable(Gujari et al., 2017).

Advanced inversion technologies employing MPPT control and IGBT components contribute to efficiency improvement and a reduction in operational costs. These technologies enable solar systems to operate better under varying environmental conditions, thus improving the overall economic viability of solar PV installations (Vishwitha et al., 2020).

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter details the procedures and approaches employed to carry out the project's primary goals. It provides details analysis of the project's execution. This comprises the selection of components to meet the specifications. The DC electricity from the solar panel passed through some components that's makes up solar based inverter system to get the AC power from it. Including in this group are the following Units in Fig 3.1 below:

Fig 3.1 Block diagram of solar based inverter system

3.1 Solar Panel

The photovoltaic system, or the solar panels, is a device that converts sunlight into electrical energy. Solar panels are a basic hardware component of any renewable energy system and find a wide range of applications from residential to commercial in order to provide a source of sustainable energy. Photovoltaic systems come basically in three types: monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and thin-film panels. Each of them has certain characteristics that determine their efficiency, cost, and suitability for a particular application. Efficiency in the case of solar panels deals with the energy-conversion

capability of sunlight into electrical energy, while cost mainly depends on the manufacturing process, the material used, and the market demand

i. Monocrystalline solar panels

Monocrystalline solar panels are made up of single crystal structure that is uninterrupted, giving it a smooth outlook and largely responsible for its efficiency in the solar panel. The efficiency ranges from 15% to 22% generally, and because of this, they have turned out to be one of the most efficient types of solar panels in today's market (Ayadi et al. 2022). They are also very durable, lasting at least 25 years or more with less than a minimal loss of efficiency throughout these years (Roy et al., 2020). However, this superior performance has a price because the monocrystalline panels are usually more expensive since the manufacturing process of the single-crystal silicon is so laborious and cumbersome.

ii. Polycrystalline photovoltaic panels

The polycrystalline photovoltaic solar panels are a result of the melting of pieces of silicon which integrate into different crystal forms. As a result of the higher element translation, it leads to decreasing the panel's efficiency that ranges between 13-16% (Ayadi et al. 2022). With this reduced efficiency, polycrystalline panels remain cheaper to manufacture. As such, they turn out to be quite popular for larger installations where cost happens to be a key factor. They would be well fitted for applications where space is not much of a constraint, like vast commercial solar farms or even ground-mounted solar systems.

iii. Thin-film solar panels

Thin-film solar panels are another approach to solar energy technology. In these panels, a thin layer of photovoltaic material is deposited on a substrate, usually made from glass, metal, or plastic. The flexibility of the thin-film panels, because of this construction, makes them light and thus suitable for applications where rigid panels could not do any practical work (Tiwari et al., 2019). The thin-film panels are generally far less efficient, lying within a range of 10% to 12%, according to (Roy et al. 2020). At the same time, their prices remain much lower to produce. Besides, they can be manufactured in many forms and sizes, thereby allowing more latitude in design.

3.1.1. Maintenance of Solar Panel

Maintenance of solar panels is important in terms of their efficiency and longevity. Recent technological advances, especially through integration with IoT and machine learning, have significantly updated maintenance strategy to predictive and efficient management of solar energy systems.

The utilization of IoT technology allows the monitoring of solar panel performance in real time, hence providing early detection for defects and helping identify potential maintenance strategies. An approach of this nature helps minimize operational maintenance costs and reduces idle hours, enabling maintenance personnel to act well in advance and prolong the life spans of panels (Babu et al., 2024).

3.1.2 Calculations to Determine Number of Solar Panel

The total number of solar panels can be estimated by the formula, with variables including the total energy requirement, the power output of each panel, and available sunlight. The formula is:

$$\text{Number of panels} = \frac{\text{TotalEnergyRequirements (Wh)}}{\text{PanelOutput (W)} \times \text{SunlightHours (h)}} \dots\dots\dots 3.1$$

3.2 Solar Charge Controller

Solar charge controllers are a valuable part of each solar energy system, as their main task is to regulate the process of charging batteries with electricity provided by solar panels. In the context of optimal storage and efficiency of the whole system, their task is very important. An SCC helps in protecting the longevity and efficiency of the batteries and solar panels through the avoidance of overcharging and ensuring the right amount of charge actually reaches the batteries.

There are two major types of SCCs: Pulse Width Modulation and Maximum Power Point Tracking, each with different operational characteristics that affect efficiency and suitability for particular installations.

i. Pulse Width Modulation (PWM)

Pulse Width Modulation controllers work by rapidly turning the solar panels' output on and off in order to maintain a consistent voltage to the batteries. The advantages with this technique include prevention of overcharging, hence controlling the flow of energy into the battery. In general, PWM controllers are usually less efficient than MPPT controllers. Therefore, as low as 80.935% efficiencies have been reported in several instances for PWM controllers. While PWM controllers are simpler and cheaper, their efficiency deviates under fluctuating sunlight conditions; therefore, they can be used for small solar installations or projects in which the economy is of essence.

ii. Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT)

Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) controllers are electronic controllers that employ special algorithms to continuously look for the electrical operating point of the

solar panels where maximum power can be extracted. Energy conversion is optimized based on the principle of adapting to sunlight intensity and temperature changes. This would, therefore, be highly effective in systems that are prone to changeable sunlight conditions. MPPT controllers have been reported to have higher efficiency levels averaging around 84.623%, thus fitting for bigger solar installations and regions whose sunlight conditions are not predictable as observed by (Pulikkottil et al).

3.2.1 Charge Controller Ratings Calculation

The rating formula of a solar charge controller that would be required within a solar-based inverter system applies to the voltage of the system and the total current being produced from the solar panels. The main formula is given by:

Let,

Charge Controller Current Rating = I_{cc}

Total Solar-Panel Wattage(W) = P_t

Battery Voltage = V_b and,

Safety Factor = SF

$$I_{cc} = \frac{P_t}{V_b} \times SF \dots\dots\dots 3.2$$

Where,

Safety Factor (SF): Normally taking care of panels variation in sunlight's intensity and temperature changes, this is an overestimation factor of 1.25 or 25%.

3.3 Battery

Batteries are one of the indispensable devices for energy storage that convert chemical energy into electrical energy in order to serve such a wide range of applications, especially in electric vehicles, renewable energy systems, and portable electronics. The basic structure of the battery consists of two electrodes: the cathode-positive terminal and the anode-negative terminal. These terminals are connected internally by an electrolyte, which provides for ionic movement between the electrodes while charging and discharging.

During a discharge, a battery has chemical reactions at the anode that give up electrons; the electrons move through the external circuit creating electrical power while ions move through the electrolyte to the cathode. It is, in fact, during the charging process that the ions begin to flow in the opposite direction to replenish the chemical potential of the battery for later use. During charging, the opposite process takes place of what occurs in the discharging process (Hasan et al., 2023).

The role of battery extends to renewable energy systems, where they have stored energy either from solar panels or from wind turbines. This will be very useful during periods when generation is low and will ensure reliability and continuity of the energy supply. Meanwhile, continued technological advances have facilitated innovation across a number of sectors owing to improvements in battery efficiency, capacity, and sustainability, rendering them a very critical building block toward a more electrified and renewable future.

Basically, batteries are of two types:

- i. Primary Batteries**

These are designed for single use, and once exhausted, they cannot be recharged. In primary batteries, the chemical reactions are irreversible, with the active materials not returning to their original state once the battery is drained. Primary batteries are thus thrown away after use, with the manufacturers warning against recharging them. These batteries are usually used in low-drain devices such as remote controls and clocks, where long-term storage and occasional use are prioritized.

ii. Secondary Batteries

The secondary batteries have the ability to be charged and used again more than once. In their construction, materials allowing reversible chemical reaction to occur in them are used, hence it provides them the ability of storing and releasing energy again and again. During discharging they convert chemical energy into electrical energy and during charging an electric current is passed in reverse direction of the chemical reaction. Chargers or any other power sources are applied through them in order to provide the required current for recharging.

3.3.1 Maintenance of the Battery

Maintenance of the battery is vital in order to ensure that performance and life are optimized. In electric vehicles and energy storage applications where demands are very high, IoT-based systems have been growing as an effective way to handle battery management. They can use sensors for real-time monitoring of such critical parameters as temperature and voltage. By integrating neural networks, these systems can perform tasks such as health tracking accurately, automating more mundane tasks, and alerting to potential issues for safety and performance improvements (Asvika et al., 2023).

Besides, predictive maintenance, employing techniques such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, promises significant advantages by making forecasts about battery failure from operational data. This proactive approach thus allows timely interventions that reduce unexpected breakdowns and prolong the life span of batteries. These predictive strategies are very helpful in automotive and industrial applications where reliability is a key concern for uninterrupted operations (Voronov et al., 2023).

3.3.2 Calculation to Determine Numbers of Battery

The equation below can be used to determine the numbers of batteries required to power an inverter system:

$$\text{Number of Batteries} = \frac{\text{Total Battery Capacity Required(Ah)}}{\text{Capacity of One Battery(Ah)}} \dots\dots\dots 3.3$$

Alternatively, number of batteries can be calculated based on energy in (watt-hour):

$$\text{Number of Batteries} = \frac{\text{Total Energy Requirements(Wh)}}{\text{Battery Voltage (V)} \times \text{Capacity of Battery(Ah)}} \dots\dots\dots 3.4$$

How to Calculate Inverter Battery Backup Time?

The numbers of batteries and their Amp-hour capacity affect the battery backup time in an inverter system. Calculations for inverter backup duration include:

$$\text{Backup time} = \frac{\text{Battery Power in (Wh)}}{\text{connected load in (W)}} \dots\dots\dots 3.5$$

Battery power in (Wh) = Battery capacity (Ah) × Battery voltage (V) × numbers of batteries

Let’s condense the formulas using following symbols:

Let,

BUT = Battery backup time in hours

C = Battery Capacity in Ah

V = Battery voltage in Volts

N = Numbers of batteries in series or parallel

PL = Connected load in watts (W)

Now,

$$BUT = C \times V \times N$$

If the selected battery is 12V, 220Ah, that is to use two 12V, 220AH connected in series and a 2.5kVA inverter.

$$C = 220Ah$$

$$V = 12V$$

$$N = 2$$

PL = 1500W (75% of the inverter rating)

$$BUT = 220 \times 12 \times 2$$

$$= 5280Wh$$

$$Backup\ time = \frac{Backup\ Power\ in\ (Wh)}{connected\ load\ in\ (W)} \dots\dots\dots 3.6$$

$$= \frac{5280}{1500}$$

$$= 3.52Hrs$$

3.4 Inverter System

The inverter is generally an electrical device that changes direct current into alternating current. All renewable systems, especially solar-based, provide electricity either directly from the panels or from batteries in DC form, which is not usable directly by most household appliances and electrical grids. The inverter fills this gap by changing the DC power into AC electricity, which most day-to-day appliances require.

The major function of the inverter is the conversion of DC electricity from solar panels or batteries into AC electricity, thus making the power suitable for most household appliances. Voltage regulation forms another important function of inverters, wherein they ensure that the output voltage is stable and appropriate for appliances. They are normally designed for converting DC voltages into standard household AC voltage; these normally convert 12V, 24V, and 48V DC voltages into 120V AC or 240V AC, depending on the region.

The inverters also provide for power optimization, such as Maximum Power Point Tracking or MPPT technology, which regulates the amount of power that can be tapped from the solar panels by continuously changing operating conditions in order to match variable sunlight intensity levels and, therefore, provide maximum energy efficiency.

Basically, inverters are of three types

i. Pure Sine Wave Inverters

The Pure Sine Wave Inverters utilize Sinusoidal Pulse Width Modulation (SPWM) techniques that provide a smooth sinusoidal wave output with minimum Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), making them suitable for the most sensitive electronic devices (Awal et al., 2022). All Pure Sine Wave Inverters are highly efficient and provide clean power compatible with most devices relying on stable and high-quality

electricity-such as medical equipment, computers, and modern appliances. The designs are further fortified with advanced control modules for the protection against voltage and current deviations, which increases their reliability and strength in solar systems, among other renewable energy installations (Pérez et al., 2022). Fig 3.2 below shown the waveform of pure sine wave inverter.

Fig 3.2: Pure Sine Wave Inverter Output Waveform

ii. Modified Sine Wave Inverters

The modified sine wave inverters have simpler designs compared to the design used by a pure sine wave inverter. They produce a stepped waveform which approximates the sine waveform as shown in Fig 3.3. These inverters, although producing higher THD, are much cheaper and sufficient for less sensitive applications with simple home appliances and power tools. They also contain essential protection features like overload and low voltage protection for both the inverter and connected devices (Design and Implementation of a Sine-Wave Inverter using Microcontroller with Modified Pulse Width Modulation Technique", 2022).

Fig 3.3: Modified Sine Wave Inverter Output Waveform

iii. Square Wave Inverters

The Square Wave Inverters have the simplest design and provide a simple square wave output with considerable harmonic distortion (Ruman et al., 2019). These are less efficient because of the high level of distortion and might damage sensitive electronics; their usage is limited only to simple applications, like simple resistive loads such as incandescent bulbs or heaters. They are not in use in contemporary modern systems because they are incompatible with most modern electronic appliances. The output waveform of square wave inverter is shown in Fig 3.4 below:

Fig 3.4: Square Wave Inverter Output Waveform

3.4.1 Inverter System Design

The three most integral parts of an inverter system function together so that the entire system may run smoothly. These units are known as Oscillation Unit, Amplification

Unit, and Transformation Unit. Each unit works with a view to converting the DC power into usable AC power with efficiency. Further in this section, we will explain the design and function of each one of these units in detail.

3.4.1.1 Oscillation Unit

The oscillatory circuit is the first most important stage of the inverter system for generation of frequency pulses. These pulses, after being amplified, drive to the gate of MOSFET drives for switching purposes. An integrated circuit (IC), normally like the SG3524 shown in Fig 3.5 below, is used for this purpose. It receives the signal at pin 11 and 14, processes it, amplifies it, and then sends this amplified signal to the MOSFET stage. In this way, the proper driving of the MOSFETs can be carried out-to convert DC power into AC. Because the oscillator in essence controls the operating frequency of the inverter, its structure determines the stability and efficiency of the power conversion process.

Fig 3.5: Configuration of SG3524 Oscillator

3.4.1.2 Power Amplification Unit

As the name suggests, it is an amplification unit that takes the pulses that come from the oscillatory unit and amplifies them to high current levels with the use of transistors called MOSFET (Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistors), other than the

traditional bipolar transistors. Unlike BJTs, MOSFETs are voltage-controlled three-terminal devices: Drain, Source, and Gate.

Basically, MOSFETs are divided into N-channel and P-channel types, each of which can be configured as either a low-side or high-side switch for driving loads. High current handling by MOSFETs and their control based on voltage are the reasons why they find applications in inverter applications: they enhance efficiency and responsiveness in the power conversion process. This is a very important amplification stage since enough power must be transferred to the load in a very stable and performance manner.

3.4.1.3 Transformation Unit

This gadget is made up of a transformer. Using the frequency, a transformer transmits electrical power from one circuit to another circuit while remaining stationary. It can raise or lower the voltage in the circuit with a corresponding decrease or increase in current. The physical basic of a transformer is mutual induction between two circuits coupled by a common magnetic flux. In its simplest form, it consists of two inductive coils that are connected magnetically but electrically by a low-reluctance path. The inductance of the two coils is very high. A generated induced EMF (The electromagnetic induction law of Faraday).

$$E = M \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \dots\dots\dots 3.7$$

$$\phi = FluxLinkage$$

E_1 is inversely proportional to the primary N_1 's number of turns as well as the pace at which the flux connecting the coil is changing. Thus, the following two significant correlations are expressed:

$$V_1 = E_1$$

$$E_1 = N_1 \left(\frac{d\phi}{dt} \right) \dots\dots\dots 3.8$$

Due to the fact that the coils are wound on the same magnetic core, the flux changes in the primary coil at the same time that it changes in the secondary coil. The flux linking the secondary and the primary coil changes at exactly the same rate since they are made of the exact same flux. The secondary windings N_2 number of turns determines the amount of induced EMF (E_2)

$$E_2 = N_2 \left(\frac{d\phi}{dt} \right) \dots\dots\dots 3.9$$

$$V_2 = E_2$$

$$\frac{E_1}{E_2} = \frac{N_1}{N_2} \dots\dots\dots 3.10$$

Let:

N_1 = No of turns in Primary

N_2 = No of turns in Secondary

The general inverter circuit characteristics would be:

Power rating: 2000W

Frequency: 50Hz

Battery input voltage: 24V DC

Inverter output voltage: 220V AC

Numbers of phases: Single phase

Cooling medium: Fan

3.4.1.4 Design Core

When the windings of a transformer with N turns are connected to an alternating voltage source, there flows a certain current in the windings. The associated current develops what is called magnetomotive force (mmf), given by the product NI with N the number of turns and I the current. This mmf in turn acts on the transformer core to produce a magnetic flux therein:

$$\phi = \phi \times \sin \omega t \dots \dots \dots 3.11$$

Where,

$$\omega = 2\pi f$$

The flux generated in the core has a minimum value of ϕ_m

The expressed provides the flow linkage.

$$\lambda = N\phi \dots \dots \dots 3.12$$

An e.m.f will be produced in the field winding provided by the due to the flux connection:

$$e = \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} \dots \dots \dots 3.13$$

$$= \frac{N \partial \phi}{\partial t}$$

$$e = \frac{N \partial (\phi_m \sin \omega t)}{\partial t}$$

$$e = N \phi_m \omega \cos \omega t$$

$$e = 2\pi f N \Phi \cos 2\pi f t \dots\dots\dots 3.14$$

the peak value of sinusoidal varying e.m.f is given by;

$$E_p = 2\pi f N \Phi m \dots\dots\dots 3.15$$

Hence, the expression of the r.m.s value, E is given by:

$$E = \frac{E_p}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{2\pi f N \Phi m}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Where,

$$\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{2}} = 4.44$$

$$E = 4.44 f N \Phi m \dots\dots\dots 3.16$$

$$\text{But } \frac{E}{N} = \text{volts per turn} = Et$$

$$Et = 4.44 f \Phi m \dots\dots\dots 3.17$$

Taking the factor r such that

$$r = \frac{\Phi m}{IN}$$

Then,

$$IN = \frac{\Phi m}{r} \dots\dots\dots 3.18$$

$$\Phi m = \sqrt{\frac{r \times 10^{-4}}{4.44 f}} \times \sqrt{kVA} \dots\dots\dots 3.19$$

$$Et = K \times \sqrt{kVA} \dots\dots\dots 3.20$$

K is a factor depending on r.

Single phase shell type transformer, the value of K varies between 1.01 and 1.25, in this design, K is 1.0

Choosing K = 1.0, where kVA is the output kVA which is 2.5kVA for this design.

$$Et = K \times \sqrt{kVA}$$

$$Et = 1.0 \times \sqrt{2.5}$$

Volts per turn (Et) = 1.58V/turn.....3.21

3.4.2 The Driver (MOSFET) Design

The oscillator produces small current while the voltage is amplified by the driver stage. The driver most commonly used in inverter projects is a power MOSFET based on the fact that it does not suffer from thermal breakdown and majorly, it aids paralleling since it has a positive on-resistance, unlike bipolar transistors which will require a current equalizing resistor. The output from the MOSFET circuit is determined by the numbers of the MOSFET used, which is a function of power handling capacity of the inverter.

3.4.3 Determination of the Numbers of MOSFET Required

The amount of MOSFETs needed for paralleling depends on the inverters 2000W maximum handling capability as well as the MOSFET maximum power dissipation.

$$Number\ of\ MOSFET = \frac{Inverter\ Handling\ Capacity}{MOSFET\ maximum\ power\ dissipated}.....3.22$$

3.5 Circuit Diagram of the System

Fig 3.6: Circuit Diagram of an inverter system

3.7 Principle of Operation of Inverter System.

The working principle of the system is such that the solar panel generates DC voltage, which is regulated by the charge controller to charge the battery. Inverter uses the energy stored in the battery for its operation. The oscillation unit inside the inverter generates a 50Hz frequency signal using power-driven MOSFETs by the voltage of the battery. This signal is then amplified by the driver unit and forwarded to the output section. In essence, this output section includes a set of switches known as MOSFETs connected to the primary winding of the transformer in the inverter. The conversion of DC into AC is controlled by the MOSFETs. By performing this switching function, the inverter can supply usable AC power to connected loads.

CHAPTER FOUR

TESTING AND RESULTS

4.1 Overview of Testing Procedure

Testing is one of the integral components of any design and construction that gives an insight into whether the system truly works the way it should and whether the specified criteria in design have been satisfied. On this project, testing is aimed at functionality testing, efficiency, load handling capability, battery performance, and safety for the 2.5kVA solar-based inverter system. All these were tested through a series of specific procedures that ensured the inverter's performance and reliability under natural conditions.

4.2 Functionality Testing

The functional test was to confirm the inverter system would operate at basic functionality: taking DC power from the solar panels and the battery into AC power. Each subsystem is tested individually. Table 4.1 below shows the details and ratings of the components utilized.

Table 4.1: Components Details

S/N	Component Name	Ratings
1	Solar Panel	320W
2	Charge Controller	60A
3	Inverter	2.5kVA

First, the solar panels were connected and the system checked for correct DC output. Under a good sunlight condition, the solar panel produced near its rating of 320W. The charge controller was handling up to 60A with no sign of overheating or other instability. DC power is inverted into a stable 230V AC output with a frequency of 50Hz. And it is confirmed that its operation is quite regular within the rated capacity.

Some minor changes to the inverter circuit were conducted to stabilize frequency, especially with varying load conditions.

4.3 Load Testing

This load test was conducted to check the inverter's capability of handling the load up to 2.5kVA-rated capacity without showing any signs of performance degradation or overheating. Load testing was done by gradually increasing the load on the inverter from a low level to 2.5kVA in steps. Output voltage, frequency, and temperature were monitored in each stage. Up to 1.5kVA, at low and average power, the inverter showed stable output voltage and frequency, while between 1.5-2.5kVA, it behaved as expected, though operating temperature rose a bit.

The system also showed very stable output throughout the tested load range, since there were no serious voltage and frequency fluctuations. The operating temperature was raised by about 15% when at maximum load, which is within acceptable limits and indicates that the inverter could reliably handle its 2.5kVA rating.

4.4 Battery Performance Testing

Performance tests of the batteries evaluated the capability of the batteries for charge and discharge cycles in addition to the general contribution they make for runtime and stability of the system. The 24V battery bank was matched with the inverter input rating for the inverter system. The battery was charged to full capacity through the 60A charge controller and then discharged under a constant load until depletion. This cycle was repeated to observe any changes in performance.

The battery provided a firm power supply and maintained the inverter output voltage for roughly 3 hours with a medium load. In general, the performance of the battery was adequate, but at low-level charge, the gradual drop in voltage disturbs output stability.

Advanced technology for the battery management system may be incorporated in future designs for improved performance.

4.5 Safety and Protection Testing

Safety and protection testing confirmed that the inverter protections, such as overcurrent and short-circuit protection and thermal protection, worked well to prevent damages. For this purpose, tests with brief overloading of the system simulated overcurrent conditions; short-circuit conditions were induced for observing the system response.

This system was designed to work this way when more load than the rated capacity was applied; it simply shut down to prevent damage. Short-circuit protection also worked in accordance with the system design and isolated the components involved. Safety mechanisms also work accordingly in this test for safe operations under harsh conditions. The charge controller, nominally rated at 60A, did not suffer any damage in current regulation to the bank of batteries.

4.6 Result

Testing of the 2.5kVA solar-based inverter system as shown in Table 4.2 below was necessary to ensure that it meets the set design specifications for reliability in operation under varying conditions. Functionality, load handling, and battery performance, together with the safety and protection, are outlined below.

Table 4.2: Results Obtained from the inverter system testing

Test Type	Parameters Monitored	Results
Functionality Testing	DC to AC conversion, frequency stability	230V AC output at 50Hz frequency; consistent

		operation within rated capacity
Load Testing	Load capacity, output stability, temperature	Stable voltage and frequency up to 2.5kVA; temperature rise of ~15% at max load
Battery Performance Testing	Charge/discharge cycles, runtime	3-hour runtime at medium load; slight voltage drop at low charge
Safety and Protection Testing	Overcurrent, short-circuit, thermal control	System shutdown on overload; successful isolation during short-circuit; charge controller stable

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

The designed solar inverter system rated at 2.5kVA was able to perform the conversion from DC to AC stably at 230V and 50Hz. Under a load of up to 2.5kVA, the inverter performed well with a minor rise in temperature. For a given medium load, the runtime duration that a battery provided was approximately 3 hours, though with slight voltage drop in low charge conditions. Safety features, like overcurrent and short-circuit protection, also functioned quite satisfactorily and thus resultantly ensured safe operation throughout testing.

5.2 Conclusion

This project proved the feasibility of a solar-based inverter system with a rating of 2.5 kVA. Energy conversion from solar to AC was done within specification bounds efficiently and safely. The results showed that solar-based inverters are reliable and efficient in renewable energy applications, providing a sustainable solution for electrical load powering in areas where access to grid power is limited.

5.3 Recommendations

All of the following recommendations represent guidelines for further work in order to attain optimization of design and functionality at various identifications to improve performance, reliability, and longevity.

- i. **System Improvements:** Developments in the future could aim at improving the efficiency of the inverters through the use of better power electronic devices in such systems. The use of more recent high-efficiency components along with control algorithms would reduce energy losses, improve energy conversion, and improve system performance.

- ii. **Component Upgrade:** Higher capacity, more energy-dense battery technologies, such as lithium-ion batteries, would significantly improve storage efficiency by minimizing voltage drops over usage periods. Such alternatives will also have an extended operational life, which allows a more reliable and persistent supply of power in residential applications.
- iii. **Enhanced Testing:** Besides, testing needs to be extended in the direction of long-term environmental tests and performance studies at various sunlight and temperature conditions to gain better insights into the system's durability. The tests for these factors would ensure that the system operates reliably under a wide range of climatic conditions.
- iv. **Design Improvements:** Inclusion of BMS will significantly help in regulating the batteries to hold a proper balance between charge/discharge cycles to minimize chances of overcharging or deep discharges that reduce battery life. The BMS would further enhance system safety and stability to maintain optimal performance of the batteries and voltage throughout the lifecycle of the inverter system.

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